

VALORISATION OF HEMP BY-PRODUCTS FOR COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: *Industrial hemp (Cannabis sativa L.) is an annual crop that requires relatively low inputs for cultivation and easily adapts to sustainable farming systems. The hemp plant is quite versatile and the resulting constituents can be used various purposes. Fibers and shives are best positioned for use in the composite related industries, because both offer distinct characteristics. Development of fungal-based composite materials from hemp shives would provide a new way for their valorization. Additionally, using shives for fungal-based bio-materials would be advantageous as they require lower energy during production, are biodegradable, and do not need added chemicals. The study's objective was to investigate a suitable hemp substrate for producing bio-composites, suitable for packaging material. Specifically, the study evaluated two white rot fungi (Ganoderma Lucidum and Trametes Versicolor) and the influence of hemp shive size, fungal culture media types, and inoculation methods. During the research, inoculation of the fungi on hemp was performed by transferring fungal material grown on solid medium and mycelium growth rate was evaluated. Substrate inoculation was divided into two stages. In the first stage, hemp shives were inoculated with fungi and in the second stage, after a certain time of fungal overgrowth, the substrate was mixed to evenly spread the overgrowth throughout the volume. Fungal overgrowth in both phases took place at 26 °C and a high relative humidity. The results of the study indicated that the growth rate is significantly influenced by the chemical composition of lignin and pH value of the substrate, with a pH value of 5 as the best condition for both types of fungi. A one week first stage, followed by a two-week second stage procedure resulted in a suitable hemp-fungi biomaterial growth. Additionally, the correct substrate preparation resulted in optimal fungi growth and higher yields of biocomposite material.*

Keywords: hemp, hemp biocomposite, hemp-fungal biomaterial